

Synergistic effects of phosphine oxides on the extraction of nickel(II) with 2-hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamide into *n*-butanol

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Abstract : The extraction behavior of nickel(II) from dilute hydrochloric acid medium using 2-hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamide (HA) and its mixture with several neutral donors e.g. tri-octylphosphine oxide (TOPO), tri-butyl phosphine oxide (TBPO) and tri-phenyl phosphine oxide (TPPO) were investigated. The extraction constants for the binary species $[\text{Ni}(\text{A})_2]$ and ternary species $[\text{Ni}(\text{A})_2(\text{B})]$ were determined, where HA = undissociated chelating agent and B = neutral donors. The result was very much in accordance with the trend in basic characters of the donors. Thermodynamic parameters were also evaluated, following the extractions under varying temperature.

Keywords : Nickel(II) extraction, synergistic effect, organophosphorus donors, 2-hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamide, AAS study.

Introduction

Synergistic extraction is a process in which there is a mutual co-operation between two extractants used in liquid-liquid transfer process of metal ions. One extractant neutralizes the charge of metal ion while other occupies open co-ordination sites in order to make the metal surface as such organophilic as possible. Under such a condition, extent of metal extraction become more than the sum of the contributions of the individual extractants¹⁻³.

Among the different classes of combination, most widely studied being the mixture of acidic extractant with neutral donors⁴⁻⁶. Chelating reagents of β -diketone type have been paid most attention^{7,8}, although use of carboxylic acid, oximes and long chain alkyl amines have also been reported⁹⁻¹¹ in case of transfer of transition metal ions from aqueous to organic phase. The most versatile class of neutral donors are alkyl or aryl substituted phosphine oxides¹². Due to the presence of electronic effect in their structure, these compounds offer electron pair in order to fill in the co-ordination shell of metal ions and at the same time their large organic tail serves to transfer such metal complexes into nonpolar organic medium.

In the present investigation synergistic effects of such substituted phosphine oxide donors on the extraction of Ni^{II} by chelating agent 2-hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamide (HA) has been reported. Synergistic extraction of Ni^{II}

adopting some other combinations like salicyldoxime and HDEHP^{13,14}, carboxylic acids and oximes^{15,16} etc. have been reported in some recent work but the study of the effects of alkyl or aryl substituted phosphine oxides on 2-hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamide (HA) have never been taken up. Present work deals with the study of enhancement of Ni^{II} extraction into *n*-butanol in presence of such a mixture. Equilibrium constants for both binary and ternary extractions were also calculated from experimental results and effects of temperature were studied in order to evaluate the thermodynamic parameters responsible for extraction mechanism.

Results and discussion

Effect of equilibration time :

Preliminary studies on the extraction of Ni^{II} by 2-hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamide in *n*-butanol show that the two phase reaction is fairly rapid and the equilibrium is reached within 15 min. The increase of the time of equilibration does not affect the extraction equilibrium.

Effect of organic diluent :

Some organic diluents like hydrocarbon, alcohol, ether, CHCl_3 etc. were chosen to study the effect of diluents upon the extraction of Ni^{II} by 2-hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamide. It has been observed that at a fixed concentration of 2-hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamide at pH 4, *n*-bu-

tyl alcohol performs best in comparison to other diluents. The trend of extraction for organic diluents used follows the order : benzene < chloroform < iso-amyl alcohol < *n*-butyl alcohol (Table 1).

Table 1. The extraction of Ni^{II} with 0.0232 mol dm⁻³ of 2-hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamide in different diluent at pH 4

Diluent	<i>D</i> ₀	% Extraction
Benzene	0.134	11.81
Chloroform	0.389	28.01
<i>iso</i> -Amyl alcohol	0.452	31.13
<i>n</i> -Butanol	0.572	36.38

Effect of pH in aqueous phase :

The pH is a very important parameter for the extraction studies¹⁷. Much of the selectivity achieved in these extractions depends on adequate control of pH¹⁸. Our experiments were carried out with different pH in aqueous phase extraction system with ligand concentration of 0.0186 mol dm⁻³ in *n*-butanol. At first, it was observed that the percentage of extraction increased with increasing pH up to 4.0, but above pH 4.0, extent of the extraction is roughly constant. The plot of log *D*₀ vs pH yields a straight line with slope ~2 indicating that, the ligand liberates two protons in the aqueous phase. In synergistic extraction with increase in pH, which may be that at higher pH, the donor becomes less effective, as there might be a competition between TOPO (donor) and H₂O molecules or OH⁻ ion (from the added alkali), resulting less involvement of TOPO in the complex of the ternary adduct, and synergism decreases. An optimum pH of 4.0 was selected for the further experiments.

Effect of ligand concentration :

Extraction of Ni^{II} from HCl medium was investigated using butanol as a diluent. The concentration of ligand [HA] was varied from 0.0093 to 0.02783 mol dm⁻³ (Table 2). The percentage of extraction was found to increase with increase in ligand concentration. At higher

Table 2. The extraction of Ni^{II} with different concentration of 2-hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamide in *n*-butanol at pH 4

Ligand	Concentration (mol dm ⁻³)	% Extraction	<i>D</i> ₀
2-Hydroxy- <i>N</i> -phenylbenzamide	0.0093	8.59	0.094
	0.0139	16.32	0.195
	0.0186	25.04	0.334
	0.0232	36.38	0.572
	0.02783	44.26	0.794

concentration of ligand, effective stripping of the water molecules take place from the hydrated metal ion sphere by the ligand, rendering the species much more organophilic in nature. The composition of extractable species was obtained from the plot of log *D*₀ vs log [ligand] (Fig. 1), and the data are fitted to a straight-line equation that gives an average slope of ~2, indicating the possi-

Fig. 1. Plot of log *D*₀ vs log [ligand] for Ni^{II}-ligand system in *n*-butanol.

bilities of two bidentate chelating groups surrounding the cation. If 'k' is the extraction equilibrium constant for the binary system, it is obviously related to distribution coefficient by equation [eq. (3)] [*D*₀ = distribution co-efficient in presence of only ligand].

$$D_0 = \frac{[\text{Ni}(\text{A})_2]_{\text{org}}}{[\text{Ni}^{2+}]_{\text{aq}}} \quad (2)$$

$$\log k = \log D_0 - 2 \log [\text{HA}] - 2\text{pH} \quad (3)$$

Effect of mixed-extractant :

Preliminary experiments show that the extent of extraction is very poor in case of pure donors, used in the present study. However when mixed with the ligand 2-hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamide, a marked enhancement in the extent of nickel extraction takes place in case of each of the three donors e.g. TOPO, TBPO and TPPO. In the ternary extraction system at a fixed concentration of ligand, increase of donor concentration increases the distribution

ratio (D_m), although to a different extent for different donors. As D_m is always greater than D_o , mixed extraction-definitely leads to synergism. Synergistic coefficient (S.C.) defined by Taube and Siekierki¹⁹ is, $S.C. = \log D_m/D_o$, since contribution of pure donor is almost nil. Such results are tabulated (Tables 3 and 4) and S.C. is found to increase with increase in donor concentration.

veals almost identical features and slopes of such straight lines are ~ 1.00 each, which indicates that only one molecule of donor is involved in mixed adduct, in all of the three ligand donor systems. On the other hand, at fixed concentration of donor log-log plot of $(D_m - D_o)$ against ligand concentration (Fig. 3) gives a straight line with slopes ~ 2 which indicates that two molecules of ligand

Table 3. Synergistic extraction of Ni^{II} by 2-hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamide and phosphine oxides at pH 4.0
[Ligand] = 1.855×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³, Distribution coefficient of Ni^{II} in presence of only ligand, $D_o = 0.334$

Donor	Concentration (mol dm ⁻³)	D_m	$(D_m - D_o)$	% Extraction	S.C.	log β
TOPO	0.00304	0.481	0.147	32.47	0.158	2.160
	0.00456	0.548	0.214	35.41	0.215	2.147
	0.00608	0.638	0.304	38.95	0.281	2.175
	0.00760	0.704	0.371	41.34	0.323	2.164
TBPO	0.00398	0.455	0.121	31.28	0.134	1.959
	0.00552	0.501	0.167	33.38	0.176	1.957
	0.00692	0.527	0.193	34.52	0.198	1.923
	0.00829	0.578	0.244	36.63	0.238	1.945
TPPO	0.00456	0.446	0.112	30.84	0.125	1.866
	0.00608	0.477	0.143	32.98	0.154	1.841
	0.00760	0.516	0.182	33.91	0.188	1.854
	0.00912	0.542	0.208	35.15	0.211	1.833

S.C. = Synergistic coefficient = $\log D_m/D_o$.

$\beta = (D_m - D_o)/D_o$ [donor], apparent formation constant.

Table 4. Synergistic extraction of Ni^{II} by mixture of chelating ligand and organophosphorus donor at a fixed concentration of donor with different concentration of ligand
pH = 4.0, Solvent = *n*-butanol

Donor concentration	Ligand concentration (mol dm ⁻³)	D_o	D_m	$(D_m - D_o)$	% Extraction	S.C.	log β
TOPO (0.0031 mol dm ⁻³)	0.0139	0.195	0.295	0.100	22.78	0.179	2.226
	0.0186	0.334	0.481	0.147	32.47	0.158	2.160
	0.0232	0.572	0.866	0.295	86.41	0.181	2.231
	0.0279	0.794	1.407	0.613	58.51	0.241	2.403
TBPO (0.00398 mol dm ⁻³)	0.0139	0.195	0.262	0.066	20.76	0.126	1.94
	0.0186	0.334	0.455	0.121	31.27	0.134	1.95
	0.0232	0.572	0.792	0.221	44.19	0.141	1.98
	0.0279	0.794	1.298	0.503	56.48	0.217	2.20
TPPO (0.00456 mol dm ⁻³)	0.0139	0.195	0.244	0.048	19.62	0.098	1.732
	0.0186	0.334	0.465	0.131	31.74	0.143	1.934
	0.0232	0.572	0.772	0.200	43.56	0.131	1.884
	0.0279	0.794	1.114	0.321	52.69	0.147	1.95

At fixed concentration of 2-hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamide, log-log plot of $(D_m - D_o)$ against donor concentration for all the three different systems (Fig. 2) re-

are involved in mixed adduct, in all of the three ligand donor combinations. Hence the overall synergistic extraction may be described as

$$K = \frac{[\text{Ni}(\text{A})_2(\text{B})]_{\text{org}} [\text{H}^+]^2_{\text{aq}}}{[\text{Ni}^{2+}]_{\text{aq}} [\text{HA}]^2_{\text{org}} [\text{B}]_{\text{org}}} \quad (5)$$

$$D_m = \frac{[\text{Ni}(\text{A})_2(\text{B})]_{\text{org}} + [\text{Ni}(\text{A})_2]_{\text{org}} + [\text{Ni}(\text{B})]_{\text{org}}}{[\text{Ni}^{2+}]_{\text{aq}}} \quad (6)$$

Fig. 2. The plot of $\log [D_m - D_o]$ vs $\log [\text{donor}]$ for synergistic solvent extraction system of Ni^{II} -ligand-neutral donor in ternary system in *n*-butanol at pH 4.0 keeping $[\text{ligand}] =$ fixed.

Fig. 3. The plot of $\log [D_m - D_o]$ vs $\log [\text{donor}]$ for synergistic solvent extraction system of Ni^{II} -ligand-neutral donor in ternary system in *n*-butanol at pH 4.0 keeping $[\text{donor}] =$ fixed.

$$\log K = \log (D_m - D_o - D_s) - 2 \log [\text{HA}]_{\text{org}} - \log [\text{B}]_{\text{org}} - 2\text{pH} \quad (7)$$

As, $D_s \approx 0$,

$$\log K = \log (D_m - D_o) - 2 \log [\text{HA}]_{\text{org}} - \log [\text{B}]_{\text{org}} - \text{pH} \quad (8)$$

where,

D_o is the distribution coefficient of Ni^{II} with 2-hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamide (HA) only and D_s is the distribution coefficient of Ni^{II} with organophosphorus donor (B) only and D_m is the distribution coefficient of Ni^{II} with 2-hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamide in presence of organophosphorus donor.

The adduct formation reaction in the organic phase may be represented as

And accordingly,

$$\log K_s = \log K - \log k \quad (10)$$

Apparent stability constants (β) of mixed-adduct in synergistic extraction is defined by

$$\beta = (D_m - D_o)/D_o [\text{donor}] \quad (11)$$

Trend in both S.C. and β -values reflected by these data indicate, TOPO > TBPO > TPPO in accordance with their basic character. From [eqs. (3) and (8)], it is possible to evaluate the equilibrium constants for the extraction with pure ligand and in case of mixed extractions after substituting other experimental parameters, as needed by these equations. The values of equilibrium constants of such binary and ternary extraction systems are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Equilibrium constant for binary and ternary extractions

Binary system	Ternary system			
	log K (average)	Donor	log K (average)	log K _s
Nickel-(2-hydroxy- <i>N</i> -phenylbenzamide)	-5.015	TOPO	-2.855	2.160
		TBPO	-3.012	2.003
		TPPO	-3.156	1.859

Effect of temperature :

In order to study the effects of temperature, equilibrations were carried out by previous method in a thermostated shaker fixed at temperatures 30, 35, 40 and 45 °C. After equilibrations, phases were separated and distribution ratio was determined.

From the data at different temperatures equilibrium constants were calculated which in turn is related by Vant-Hoff equation.

$$\log K = -\Delta H^0/2.303RT + \Delta S^0/2.303R \quad (12)$$

and

$$\Delta G^0 = \Delta H^0 - T \Delta S^0 \quad (13)$$

where ΔG^0 , ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 are thermodynamics parameters and R is universal gas constant. The [eq. (12)] shows that the plot of $\log K$ against $1/T$ will result a straight line as shown by Fig. 4. for ligand-donor system. Enthalpy

Fig. 4. Temperature variation of equilibrium constants in *n*-butanol at pH 4.0.

(ΔH^0) and entropy (ΔS^0) terms may be calculated from the slope and intercepts of such straight lines with respect to each of the three donors. In Table 6, all the thermodynamic parameters for the mixed extraction-systems are presented. From these values it is clear that the adduct complex formation reaction proceeds endothermically with entropy gain at the standard state conditions²⁰. ΔH^0 values should gain higher positive values with increasing

basicities of the donor as well as steric factors. The entropy gain is explained by the extensive disruption of the hydration sphere which is a feature of the inner-sphere complexes, with subsequent release of more water molecules. Therefore synergistic extraction of Ni^{2+} by all the phosphine oxides donor is explained by the replacement of the coordinated water molecule from primary coordination sphere of the metal.

Infra-red spectroscopy :

The infra-red spectrum of the extracted compound was recorded in organic solution, by evaporating *n*-butanol solvent. The infra-red spectrum of extracted metal-ligand complex shows that the ν_{N-H} and $\nu_{C=O}$ band frequency has shifted to the little down field from in the free ligand. In the IR spectrum of the free ligand broad band at 3390–3150 cm^{-1} is assigned to ν_{N-H}/ν_{O-H} and the band due to $\nu_{C=O}$ is observed at 1683 cm^{-1} . In complexes the band due to ν_{O-H} is disappeared indicating the possible loss of proton on complexation and subsequent formation of a M–O bond. A new band appear in the spectra at 605 cm^{-1} of extracted complexes which is characteristic of Ni–O bond²¹. The band due to $\nu_{C=O}$ shifts to the lower frequency at 1675 cm^{-1} in the complexes, thus showing the coordination of C=O group to the metal atom. Similarly the $\nu_{P=O}$ band has been shifted from 1145 cm^{-1} in free phosphine oxide donor to 1121 cm^{-1} which characterize the P–O–Ni bond in mixed adduct complex. All these data clearly support the formation of the adduct complex is $[Ni(A)_2(B)]$ in the organic phase.

Experimental

A Systronics model 335 digital pH meter equipped with a single electrode was used for pH measurements. Infrared spectra of ligands and adduct complexes were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer FTIR Model RX1 spectrometer in the range 4000–200 cm^{-1} in KBr discs. A Varian Model Spectra 55B flame atomic absorption spectrometer (AAS) was used for measuring the concentration of Ni^{II} in aqueous phase in an air-acetylene flame. A stock solution of Ni^{II} was prepared by dissolving 0.5 g $NiCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (AR) in deionised water and was standardised by complexometric titration²². Neutral donors like TOPO, TBPO and TPPO were collected from M/s Sigma-Aldrich Chemical Co. All other chemicals and solvents used were of AR grade.

Table 6. Thermodynamic parameters for Ni^{II} -(2-hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamide)-phosphine oxide donor

System	ΔH^0 (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^0 (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔG^0 (kJ mol ⁻¹)
Ligand	22.12 ± 0.8	-25.76 ± 0.10	29.85 ± 2.0
Ligand + TOPO	30.71 ± 2.0	46.87 ± 0.15	16.647 ± 1.0
Ligand + TBPO	28.31 ± 2.0	35.85 ± 0.15	17.544 ± 1.0
Ligand + TPPO	27.55 ± 2.5	30.47 ± 0.2	18.407 ± 1.2

In the general extraction procedure, an aqueous solution containing ~100 µg/ml of Ni^{II} adjusted to pH 4.0 was equilibrated for 15 min with an equal volume of organic phase containing 2-hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamide (HA) (E. Merck) in *n*-butanol. For synergistic studies, the organic phase was a mixture of chelating ligand and donor in appropriate ratio. After equilibration, the aqueous phase was disengaged and analysed for its absorbance by AAS. Concentration of metal ion in organic phase was calculated by the difference from original concentration of the metal. Distribution ratio was computed from the ratio of concentrations of metal in organic and aqueous phase. For the study of the temperature effect, equilibrations were carried out in a temperature controlled mechanical shaker, after which distribution ratio were determined in usual way.

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